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Lived Experiences of Paralympic Coaches in the Division of Capiz

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Abstract

This study, employing a qualitative Grounded Theory design, aimed to determine the lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and aspirations of Paralympic coaches across different Special Education Schools in the Division of Capiz. An informal interview guide was used to gather data through in-depth interviews with ten purposively selected participants. Themes were extracted using thematic and narrative analysis. Data revealed that the coaches have varied experiences with their athletes and their parents, as well as other factors beyond their control. The athletes displayed emotional instability, such as throwing tantrums, making alibis, laziness, shyness, and nervousness, and with unsupportive parents. Coaches cannot attend to their classes during training and competitions; lack of clear mechanics in Paralympics; scarcity of resources and equipment; and indefinite guidelines for higher competition. Coaches have developed coping mechanisms they apply to their athletes, themselves, and others. Though the coaches have already established a positive coping mechanism, they still have aspirations for their athletes, for themselves, and for others, which they view as of great importance for the improvement of Paralympics in Capiz Division. A proposed intervention plan for Paralympics coaching was conceptualized based on the study's results. It is recommended that the sports committee of the Department of Education support the quarterly training and seminars for athletes' coaches; extend financial assistance to athletes and coaches; and develop concrete policies and guidelines for the conduct of Paralympics at all levels.

Keywords: Lived Experiences, Coping Mechanisms, Aspirations, Qualitative Research